

SOLVOTHERMAL METHOD FOR RECYCLING HYBRID COMPOSITE MATERIALS

A. T. Quitain¹, K. Shibata², F. Kawase¹, K. Nasu¹, M. Sasaki^{1*}, M. Goto³

¹Graduate School of Science and Technology, Kumamoto University, Kumamoto, Japan

²Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd. Ibaraki, Japan

³Department of Chemical Engineering, Nagoya University, Nagoya, Japan

* Corresponding author (msasaki@kumamoto-u.ac.jp)

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1 Introduction

Increasing global demand for hybrid composite materials in aerospace, automotive and electronic industries has also resulted in accumulation of related solid wastes [1]. Automobile composite wastes had reached 60,000 tons worldwide in 2011, while commercial aircrafts built in carbon and epoxy-resin based composites may reach end-of-life in a fast annual rate of 100 units. No standard recycling methods are available, and most of these materials are being scrapped and disposed into landfill. However, strict government policies and legislations shall be implemented to curb these imminent environmental problems. For example, European Union legislation will demand all manufacturers to recycle end-of-life vehicles, aiming 85% recycle rate by 2015 [2]. Thus, recycling and reuse are unavoidable and shall be part of its industrial manufacturing processes.

Several methods of recycling have been proposed including mechanical and thermal as summarized by

Pickering [3]. The mechanical approach reduces the size of the scrap to produce recyclates, while the thermal methods convert the scrap into useful materials, while producing energy in the process. The thermal processes mentioned in the report include combustion, the use of fluidized bed and pyrolysis. Many other methods have been proposed including the use of subcritical and supercritical fluids of water and alcohols.

Application of sub and supercritical fluids is a new approach for recycling composite materials. Decomposition of thermoset polymeric matrix materials of composites proceeds rapidly in supercritical fluids compared to conventional methods [3, 4]. From 79.3% decomposition rate using supercritical water; the decomposition reaction can be further improved to 95.4% with the addition of KOH as a catalyst [5]. Moreover, decomposition reaction can reach 95% with supercritical alcohols in semi-continuous flow systems [6, 7]; n-propanol is also being used for this purpose [8]. Moreover, very

Fig. 1. Proposed CFRP recycling concept using solvothermal method for simultaneous recovery of carbon fiber and chemical degradation of polymeric composite resin materials.

clean fibers can be recovered, maintaining 98% of tensile strength of virgin fibers [9]. It has also proven that the use of different additives could make the properties of recovered fibers even better after treatment with supercritical fluid [10].

As a promising recycling technique, application of solvothermal method using benzyl alcohol (BZA) has been proposed by our research group [11,12].

In this present work, application of solvothermal method using benzyl alcohol (BZA) as a solvent to recover fibers by degradation of polymer resins to recycle spent hybrid composite materials is investigated as shown in the proposed recycling concept in **Fig. 1**. Degradation behavior is elucidated by analyzing decomposition rate and products. The recovered fibers were also characterized by SEM, TG-DTA and DSC analyses.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample

Samples (5mm×20mm×0.1mm) in **Fig. 2** were provided by Fujikura Composites Co. and Hitachi Chemical Co. 99% pure BZA and K₃PO₄ with purity of more than 95% were purchased from Wako Pure Chemical Industries (Wako, Japan).

Fig. 2. Sample CFRP test sheet and molecular structure of epoxy resin (24%) in the sample.

2.2 Experimental Methods

The apparatus for solvothermal experiments (AKICO Co. Japan) shown in **Figs. 3 and 4** consists of a batch-type Inconel reactor (about 8.8 cm³ inner volume) and a heating electric furnace. Mechanical stirring of reactor is provided with a cyclic horizontal swing span of 2 cm fixed at a frequency

of 60 cycles per minute. The amount of solvent used in each experiment is almost half the volume of the reactor. Water and benzyl alcohol were used as solvents for decomposition experiments. Critical temperatures (T_c) and pressures (P_c) for water and benzyl alcohol are T_c = 375°C, P_c = 22.1 MPa and T_c = 403°C, P_c = 4.6 MPa, respectively. It took about 15 min to reach the set reaction temperature of 210 to 300 °C. The reaction time was varied from 0.5 to 8h. After the reaction time has elapsed, batch reactor was quenched in a water bath for rapid cooling. The degradation products and fibers were then separated for analyses. The degradation rate (DR) was then calculated from the amount of resin removed from the sample on the basis of the amount of resin originally present, and reported in %.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the reactor and actual apparatus for solvothermal experiments (T_{max}=500°C, P_{max}=50MPa)

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of experimental apparatus showing batch reactor inside the electric furnace (arrows indicate cyclic horizontal movement for mixing of samples inside the reactor)

2.3 Analysis of the Products

GC-MS analyses of the degradation products were carried out using a Hewlett Packard-HP 6890 GC-MS apparatus. Separation was carried out using a non-polar HP-5MS capillary column with He as a carrier gas. The sample volume was 0.5µl, and was injected in splitless mode. The oven temperature was initially at 45 °C, then was ramped up to 300 °C at an initial rate of 6 °C/min, then was increased to 10°C/min after reaching 220°C. The surfaces of recovered fibers were characterized by SEM (JEOL JSM-6390LV) analyzer. The recovered fibers were also analyzed by thermogravimetric-differential thermal analyzer (TG-DTA) and by differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) to test its thermal properties in comparison with the virgin fiber.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Comparison of Various Solvents

Using 0.7g CFRP sample, degradation of polymer resins using benzyl alcohol (BZA), the primary solvent used in this study, was compared with other solvents at T=300 °C. Results in Fig. 5 show that BZA was the most effective solvent compared to H₂O and EtOH (DR=18.9%, not shown), giving degradation rate (DR) above 67%. The degradation rate (DR) was also found dependent on treatment time and temperature, and with the addition of tripotassium phosphate (K₃PO₄) catalysts.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the obtained samples after treatment using various solvents at T=300 °C, in 0.5h

3.2 Evaluation of Various Catalysts on Degradation of Polymer Resin

Fig. 6 summarizes the effect of various catalysts on the degradation of composite materials. The use of acid, base or salt catalysts resulted into decomposition rates higher than 80%. However, on the environmental point of view, and to minimize corrosion of reactor, the use of salt catalysts such as tripotassium phosphate (K₃PO₄) is preferable over acid or base catalysts. Thus, K₃PO₄ was used in this study for experiments involving catalysts.

Fig. 6. Comparison of catalytic activities of various types of catalysts

3.3 Effect of K₃PO₄ Catalysts Addition

At the same conditions mentioned above, addition of K₃PO₄ catalysts increased the degradation rate of the resin by 27.6% from 67.2% without catalysts, obtaining DR of 94.8% as shown in Figs. 5&7. In the presence of small amount of water at BZA:H₂O molar ratio of 9:1, almost complete degradation were obtained as compared to only 61.0% without catalysts. Using pure H₂O as a solvent, the DR also increased with the addition of catalysts, however, the degradation is still low compared to those obtained using BZA. Almost complete degradation of the resin was attained by doubling the reaction time from 30 min to 1 h with or without catalysts as also shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Photographs showing obtained fibers with or without K_3PO_4 catalysts ($T = 300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Fig. 8. SEM images of the obtained fibers ($T = 300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $t = 1\text{ h}$) with two different rates of magnification (700x and 2,000x)

Fig. 9. Comparison of degradation rate obtained from atmospheric and high-pressure treatments of CFRP samples.

Fig. 10. Typical GC-MS chromatograms of degradation products of epoxy resin under high-pressure conditions.

Compound(s) Sample	BZA Benzaldehyd Bibenzyl	BPA heptane	Amine compounds		
CFRP (atmospheric)	○	○	×	×	×
CFRP (pressurized)	○	○	○	○	○

Table 1. Comparison of the components obtained from the degradation of epoxy resin under atmospheric and solvothermal conditions.

3.4 SEM Images of Obtained Fibers

The SEM images of obtained fibers are shown in **Fig. 8** for solvothermal BZA treated samples with or without K_3PO_4 catalysts. SEM photographs showed clean images especially in the presence of K_3PO_4 catalysts, indicating the advantages of the proposed method for recovery of the fibers along with degradation of the chemical composites.

3.5 Effect of Pressure

Fig. 9 shows comparison of the experimental results obtained at 210 °C under atmospheric pressure, and at 300 °C under near-critical pressure of 9 atm and various reaction times. Results indicate that it would take only half the time to attain complete degradation of the resin when working with near-critical pressure compared to the atmospheric pressure.

3.6 Analysis of Degradation Products

Typical GC-MS analysis of the polymer resin degradation products is shown in **Fig. 10**. Results of analysis show the presence of amine and ester monomers, and compounds related to BZA decomposition and reaction with the polymer resins. Still, several peaks could not be accurately identified based on comparison with the compounds stored in NIST database. These compounds were also likely related to the decomposition of the epoxy polymer resin in the sample.

Amine-containing compounds and some other aromatic compounds shown in **Table 1** were not detected at atmospheric conditions but were observed present in solvothermal treated degradation products (under pressure).

4. Application to Recycling of Carbon Fiber Golf Shaft

The method was applied to recycling of carbon fiber golf shaft provided by Fujikura Composites Co, Ltd. In this case, treatment was first carried out using BZA as a solvent at a temperature of 210 °C, under atmospheric pressure for 8h in the presence of K_3PO_4 catalysts. With this treatment method, almost complete degradation of the resin sample was observed. However, some of the decomposed resins remained adhering on the surface of the fiber, thus further treatment was applied using the proposed solvothermal method. In this second step, further degradation was carried out using the same BZA solvent at a temperature of 300 °C ($P=1.0$ MPa) for 8h, in the presence of K_3PO_4 catalyst (10x lower than the first step). The experimental conditions and images of the recovered fibers are summarized in **Fig. 11**, showing almost complete degradation (99%) of the resin as also depicted in enlarged images of the recovered fibers. SEM images also confirmed the recovered fibers to be clean, damageless and well-dispersed.

Fig. 11. Application of the combined atmospheric and solvothermal treatment methods for the recovery of carbon fibers from golf shaft.

5. Application to Recycling of Tantalum Capacitor

A tantalum capacitor can be seen in almost electronic circuits. Typically, this contains pellet of tantalum metal that serves as anode, covered by insulating oxide layer that forms the dielectric. This is surrounded by conductive material, serving as a cathode as shown in **Fig. 12**. Tantalum, a rare metal is mainly used for these capacitors.

With expected high demand for tantalum capacitors due to booming electronic industries, a recycling technology to recover this expensive and rare metal from spent tantalum capacitor should be developed. Application of solvothermal BZA method was also investigated. Unlike CFRP and golf shaft, decomposition of this capacitor would require relatively higher temperatures above 300 °C, with maximum obtained degradation rate of only about 35%.

Fig. 12. Basic structure of a tantalum capacitor

6. Summary of the Results

Benzyl alcohol (BZA) under atmospheric and pressurized (or solvothermal) condition is a good solvent for chemical recycling of thermoset composite materials, obtaining very clean carbon fibers after treatment. High degradation rate close to 100% can be obtained in short time of 1h, especially in the presence of K_3PO_4 catalysts. SEM photographs of recovered fibers also showed clean images, indicating advantages of the proposed methods for recycling of chemical composites along with recovery of the fibers.

The use of BZA looks promising due to relatively low critical pressure compared with supercritical water or any alcohol. Results have shown the feasibility of the method to recover the carbon fibers from thermoset composite materials, and the outlook seems positive for process commercialization. However, several factors should be taken into account prior to commercialization of the process including costs, types of reactors, environmental issues with solvents and residues, gas emissions, decomposition rates and mechanical properties of recovered fibers.

Application of the methods to recycling of carbon fiber golf shaft and tantalum capacitor had also shown advantages. The combined atmospheric and solvothermal approaches worked well with golf shaft, obtaining almost complete decomposition of the resin. Clean, undamaged and well-dispersed fibers were recovered. However, tantalum capacitor would require severe conditions of temperature above 300 °C, and still yet a low decomposition rate of 35% was obtained.

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